

Educational Assessment in Philosophy According to the Competency-Based Pedagogy

HAMDI LAKHEL

Professor, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Mohamed Kheider, Biskra, Algeria
ORCID, 0009-0009-6433-1144

Abstract

This article aims to reveal the truth that the development of teaching philosophy, along with various pedagogical processes such as educational assessment, has made the subject of philosophy compatible with modern pedagogies, despite this not being a new concept, philosophy is the mother of educational work and pedagogical action, assessment in philosophy has been able to respond to the requirements of competency-based pedagogy, enhancing its role, lifting burdens that constrained it, and refining its mission.

Today, in sync with this new approach, philosophy has become a leading academic subject that helps learners acquire logical thinking skills, elevate the authority of balanced thinking, stimulate them to research, think, and analyze, and encourage the practice of critical thinking, it also motivates them to understand reality and adapt to current problems, despite obstacles that sometimes hinder this, assessment in philosophy according to the competency-based approach, remains of great importance, placing it at the core of philosophical activities.

Keywords: Educational Assessment, Philosophy, Competency-based Pedagogy.

1. Introduction

Assessment is considered one of the components of the educational system, a crucial element of educational policy, and a fundamental pillar of pedagogical action, it is a significant aspect of the educational process, and many education and pedagogy scholars describe it as the "lungs" of the educational process, as it derives effectiveness and efficiency from it, through assessment, strengths and weaknesses in the educational system are identified, paving the way for addressing imbalances, overcoming difficulties, and facilitating obstacles to achieve educational quality.

It outlines the major features of the educational system, including its political, economic, social, and cultural dimensions across various knowledge acquired by learners through different educational curricula and programs for various subjects such as philosophy, philosophy often raises several educational and pedagogical questions, including how to assess, assessment methods, and more.

Educational assessment in the subject of philosophy, according to the competency-based pedagogy, has distinctive characteristics and features, while traditional assessment in philosophy relied on cognitive quantity and motivation for memorization, restricting the learner's freedom in thinking and creativity, assessment in philosophy according to the competency-based approach, has evolved, it now aligns with the new pedagogy that is based on the concepts of learning, freedom, practical and functional aspects of knowledge, among others.

This article aims to reveal the nature of educational assessment in philosophy according to the competency-based pedagogy; hence, the following issues will be addressed: what is the nature of educational assessment in philosophy according to the competency-based pedagogy? What are its characteristics and features?

2. The Definition of Educational Assessment

In modern education, it is defined as "the process that aims to assess the achievement of educational goals and the effectiveness of the entire educational program, including planning, implementation, and educational methods and means". (Alam, 2023, p. 10)

Based on this definition, educational assessment is linked to the achievement of competencies and educational goals behind any educational effort, specific teaching process, academic level, or even through a particular lesson or educational activity, assessment is concerned with identifying the strengths and weaknesses in the curriculum and educational program, it aims to assess the quality and effectiveness of the methods used in education.

Therefore, assessment becomes a type of evaluation, adjustment, and reform for various components of the educational system to correct errors and move from a state of discord and inconsistency to a state of integration and harmony.

As an example, consider the assessment of a philosophy teacher for a lesson with their students. This assessment aims to understand the extent of the students' comprehension of the lesson and the concepts presented, as well as their ability to solve problems related to it.

This may involve evaluating their proficiency in providing correct answers to questions about the lesson, such as writing a philosophical essay related to the previous lesson.

Furthermore, assessment is also defined as: "a process that takes place at the end of specific educational tasks with the aim of informing the student and the teacher about the degree of mastery achieved, it aims to discover the areas of difficulty encountered by the student during their learning, enabling them to discover strategies that facilitate their development, it encourages viewing mistakes as attempts to solve problems, moments of learning, rather than mere weaknesses, formative assessment also enables identifying the learner's qualifications to embark on new stages of learning in a sequential manner, it can also rectify teaching gaps". (Hamdan, 1984, pp. 22-23)

Assessment is linked to the level of learning, aiming to identify errors and flaws for the purpose of addressing them, this includes flaws in the methods and techniques adopted in education and teaching, as well as the teacher's awareness of gaps in the teaching process, such as the ineffectiveness of pedagogical methods or the lack of logical coherence and sequencing of educational units. It may also involve shortcomings in providing realistic examples that help learners understand, among other challenges in the field of education, assessment serves to fill these gaps and correct errors, ensuring the achievement of competencies and goals in the educational process, as an example, a teacher might find that their students have not understood a lesson even after an extended explanation, in such a case, assessment comes into play to review the lesson, using real-life examples and a flexible and easy-to-understand approach to help students comprehend and absorb the material.

3. Philosophy: Concept and Topics

3.1 The Concept of Philosophy

Human beings have recognized various modes of thought throughout history, among which is philosophical thinking, Philosophy is defined as a rational theoretical knowledge that aims to study, analyze, and criticize the understanding of various phenomena related to human beings, life, the universe, and existence in its dimensions and manifestations.

The term "philosophy" comes from the Greek word "philosophia", meaning the love and pursuit of wisdom. In ancient Greece, those engaged in the pursuit of wisdom were called philosophers, as noted by Pythagoras (died around 600 BCE). (Toumi, 2009, p. 05)

However, defining the meaning of philosophy is challenging due to differences among philosophers, thinkers, and researchers in precisely framing its definition.

For instance, Plato (427-347 BCE) sees philosophy as the search for the beautiful order of existence, aiming to understand the creator, according to him, philosophy combines ethical wisdom that transcends the concerns of individual life with the study of the world's principles, and the study of human psychology in terms of knowledge and behavior. (Baddawi, 1975, p. 08)

In addition, Ibn Rushd (1126-1198 CE) sees philosophy as the consideration of existents, their indication of the creator, and the intellectual contemplation of principles of absolute existence and their ultimate causes. (Abid Al-Jabiri, 1998, p. 99)

In the modern era, philosophy shifted from investigating existence to exploring knowledge. For example, Francis Bacon (1561-1626 CE) considers philosophy as setting individuals aside, indifferent to initial impressions, focusing on abstracted meanings derived from them, according to him, philosophy encompasses the first philosophy, creative philosophy, and natural philosophy. (Baddawi, 1975, pp. 09-10)

At the beginning of the 20th century, philosophy turned towards human inquiry, giving rise to major philosophical schools such as pragmatism, existentialism, realism, and analytical philosophy, among others.

Philosophy, as a distinctive form of knowledge, thus changes its subject of inquiry from one era to another, expressing explicit reflections of human crises and problems that vary from one age to another.

3.2 Philosophical Topics

Philosophy delves into three major topics: the existence topic, the value topic, and the knowledge topic.

3.2.1 Ontology (Existence Topic)

Ontology is considered the fundamental field of philosophical theory, also known as metaphysics, its primary concern is the absolute, ultimate truth, abstract universals, issues, and established principles, Philosophy, when exploring truth, raises questions such as whether truth is absolute or relative, and whether it is connected to reality or to humanity, such questions form the basis for metaphysics, which investigates existence: Is it material or spiritual, or a combination of both? It explores the universe and human existence using reason, examining teleological causes, suggesting that the cosmos is organized based on goals, metaphysics interprets things and events in the universe and the world based on outcomes, it also examines other concepts like causality, existence and essence, possibility and choice, freedom and sin, time and space, and immortality and annihilation.

Metaphysics introduces discussions and questions in the realm of theory and educational practices that lack scientific answers. For instance, does human life have a purpose? If so, what is it, and can it truly be achieved? It's worth noting that many scholars consider ontology to be synonymous with metaphysics and ontology.

3.2.2 Axiology (Value Topic)

The value topic is considered a fundamental aspect of philosophy. Philosophy, uniquely, addresses and analyzes various value-related problems that pertain to the behavior of both individuals and communities, It raises questions such as: What are ethics? Who determines them? Are ethics inherent only to humans, or do they extend to animals? What is the nature of ethics? Are they absolute or relative? What is their criterion: religion, reason, utility, or society? Philosophers attempt to provide solutions or perspectives for these questions.

Due to the enduring interest of philosophers in ethical issues throughout the ages, ethical philosophy emerged, this branch investigates absolute values and ideals such as goodness, truth, justice, and more.

3.2.3 Epistemology (Knowledge Topic)

Metaphysical questions lead to inquiries about knowledge, investigating the possibility of understanding the universe and existence or the inability to comprehend them, epistemology explores the nature of knowledge: Is it of a mental or empirical nature? Can humans perceive truths and be certain about the accuracy of their perceptions and information, or is there doubt about their ability to know? What are the limits of human knowledge? Is it certain or probabilistic? Does knowledge come to humans through reason, senses, intuition, or experience? These issues fall under what is known as the theory of knowledge.

Some philosophers argue that philosophical thinking is a process of coordinating various fields of knowledge, each exploring a facet of experience, it serves as a connector between these diverse knowledge domains, making the knowledge topic crucial in philosophy. (Jaanini, 2004)

4. The Competency Approach: Concept and Foundations

The competency-based approach is a method for preparing lessons and educational programs through:

- Precise analysis of situations in which learners are or will be involved.
- Identification of the competencies required to perform tasks and bear the responsibilities resulting from them.

(Al-Toumi, 2008, p. 302)

It is an educational and pedagogical approach that transforms learning into a purposeful act to adapt to reality and solve life problems by employing acquired knowledge and integrating it to address various situations.

This is achieved through the learner acquiring competencies, represented by abilities and skills that aid in understanding and effectively navigating life.

As for the principles underlying the pedagogy of competencies They are based on the results obtained in various psychological and educational sciences and modern theories in psychology, such as cognitive theory, constructivist theory, developmental psychology, differential psychology, and intelligence theories.

It is worth noting that the Algerian educational system, through the educational reforms in 2003, adopted the competency-based pedagogy as a strategic educational and pedagogical choice, this shift was deemed essential due to its effectiveness and importance in the educational process, aligning with local and international developments that necessitate adjustments, changes, and reforms in the pedagogical structure of the educational system, the adoption of this new pedagogy, the competency-based approach, in developing curricula, educational

programs, and preparing textbooks, is an educational and pedagogical necessity, it aligns with global educational systems and is recognized by international educational organizations such as UNESCO, which continually provides guidance and suggestions in line with this pedagogy, it's essential to note that discussing the competency-based approach as an effective pedagogical method does not mean it alone achieves the intended educational purpose, other pedagogical approaches, including error-based pedagogy, project-based pedagogy, differential pedagogy, support pedagogy, and others, are integral to and included within the competency-based approach.

5. Examples of Educational Activities in Philosophy

Philosophers and specialized pedagogues in the teaching of philosophy agree that educational activities in philosophy can be categorized into three main types: philosophical theoretical lesson, philosophical text, and philosophical article.

5.1 The Philosophical Lesson

The philosophical lesson differs from lessons in other subjects, as it expresses the nature, message, topics, and methodology of philosophy, its content discusses issues of life, existence, and the universe issues that cannot be touched or seen with the naked eye. These are matters beyond the physical, metaphysical issues such as the problem of freedom, responsibility, punishment, the soul, and others.

These are imaginary issues discussed only at the theoretical level, the philosophical lesson does not present ready-made content to the learner but rather starts from questioning reality, representing real problems that stimulate the desire for knowledge and the search for answers, questions such as, 'Are we free or constrained? If we are free, how do we explain the social determinisms that constrain us?'

These questions lead to serious thinking based on doubt about commonly accepted facts in society, resulting in astonishment and embarrassment, hence, the value of the philosophical question that challenges the mind, stirs emotions, and stimulates curiosity to uncover the truth and combat ignorance, this infinite task is a continuous struggle as long as humans, as rational beings, maintain an unbroken curiosity for questioning. (Ministry of National Education, 2007, p. 37)

Moreover, the lesson, in its methodology, is constructed as an integrated, harmonious unit with introduction, presentation, and conclusion, the appropriate method for the philosophical lesson to achieve its goals is the dialogical method through questioning and answering, the learner engages in thinking, analysis, and the application of various mental activities, here, we move to the essence of philosophy, which is philosophizing. Therefore, the philosophical lesson, according to Kant, will not achieve its goals unless it opens up space for the learner to enjoy the freedom of thought and the spirit of criticism, using arguments and evidence in acceptance or rejection and dealing with issues and problems objectively, starting from reason and reality, thus, teaching philosophy without explaining philosophical methods is mere memorization of ideas with no benefit. (Waezize, 1990, p. 11)

Frederick Nietzsche (1844-1900 A.D) calls for the liberation of the philosophical lesson. He suggests not restricting the philosophy teacher and student to specific curricula and contents but opening a space for intellectual clash and cultural conflict, resulting in an elevated individual who managed to excel and surpass others. This can only be achieved by learning the correct perception of things, followed by learning to think, and then learning to read, we learn all of this just as we learn to dance according to its rules. Nietzsche says: 'We cannot exclude dance in all its forms from delicate education. One should know how to dance with one's thoughts and words'. (Nietzsche, 1996, p. 247)

From this, it becomes clear that the philosophical lesson, as an educational and pedagogical activity for teaching philosophy, differs in its subject, methodology, and approach. What makes it create the distinction that sets philosophy apart from other forms of knowledge, the educational assessment of the philosophical lesson aims to evaluate everything related to the completion of the lesson: methods, approaches, curricula, and programs, it ensures that the teacher and the student reach their levels to the correct and effective ways of accomplishing and teaching philosophical lessons.

5.2 The Philosophical Text

Many specialists in the philosophy education field agree that the philosophical text is the most important educational and pedagogical activity because it directly engages the teacher and the student with the philosopher's language and ideas without intermediaries. The choice of suitable texts that serve the purpose and align with theoretical lessons is crucial. the textual approach in teaching philosophy through texts has proven successful in many countries such as Morocco, Germany, England, and others, the philosophical text enables the student to learn philosophical methods, thinking and analysis mechanisms, understanding, and explanation, it

helps them acquire problem-solving methods and practice philosophical writing in light of the issues presented in the texts.

A text is pedagogically effective only if it meets conditions such as precision, control, containing a specific problem, being concise, and being accessible to the student, Hegel emphasizes that the most important characteristic of the philosophical text is its focus on reviewing the most important theories and ideas left by philosophers to be understood, evaluated, and used to build a philosophical perspective on various issues and problems. Hence, Hegel rejects Kant's view of the philosophical lesson, considering it limited, how can philosophy be taught without teaching the history of philosophy? This is evident in his valuable book 'The Phenomenology of Spirit,' where he directly criticizes arguments that reject teaching philosophy. (Bodoma, 2002, p. 43)

This perspective is also embodied in his teaching of his students, emphasizing that the philosophical text cannot emerge from a vacuum but must have introductions and preludes, it should build upon what predecessors have written in the field of philosophy and their philosophical contributions, the philosophical text trains the learner to understand ideas and deal with issues, building a general understanding of philosophical sources.

Educational assessment is present in philosophical texts, as teachers often evaluate their students and guide them on understanding and analyzing the text, pointing out weaknesses and errors for correction.

5.3 The Philosophical Essay

The philosophical essay is considered one of the most important practical activities in the subject of philosophy, it represents directed work and practical activity based on what has been covered in theoretical lessons, therefore, it receives attention from both students and teachers alike, the philosophical essay revolves around writing an article on a philosophical question according to a specific plan and methodology, this is evident today in official exams, where students are asked to write a philosophical essay addressing the content and substance of these questions.

Philosophical essays vary depending on the structure and nature of the question, there are argumentative essays, investigative essays presented in an affirmative or negative manner, as well as comparative essays, among the merits of the philosophical essay is helping the learner showcase their competencies in understanding and analysis. It becomes an effective activity that promotes positive thinking and successful philosophizing, contributing to the development of an independent personality that believes in reason, logic, argumentation, and evidence.

Kant emphasizes that every human is a philosopher as long as they engage in the acts of thinking, analysis, and criticism, practicing philosophy by seeking truth without submitting to the authority of a specific philosopher's method or approach, philosophy, according to him, is the art of correct thinking and good philosophizing, this is achieved by stripping the philosophical essay from ready-made templates and imposed theories that some urge to read and memorize, this contradicts the true nature and goals of the philosophical essay, which is considered a powerful cry against conformity and submission, Kant once shouted, affirming that if philosophy were about memorizing our books in one book, we would tell you to read this book, and you would become philosophers, however, philosophy is far from that; it is a distinct knowledge representing an intellectual adventure and a research experience in understanding the truth of things and phenomena, its mission is to stimulate thought to think, to understand, and to instill critical thinking, it neither accepts nor rejects except with clear evidence, it is an education for intellectual independence in the mind of the learner. (Boudabous, 1996, p. 11)

Referring to the educational assessment of the philosophical essay, it has two aspects, first, evaluating students' answers in exams and giving them the deserved grade based on their content, methodology, language, and other factors. Second, providing guidance and giving useful feedback that helps the student improve their level and avoid repeating those mistakes and shortcomings.

6. Characteristics of Educational Assessment in Philosophy

The educational assessment in the philosophy subject is characterized by several competencies, features, and qualities including:

6.1 Learner's Freedom

The learner is considered the focal point of the teaching-learning process in the competency-based pedagogy, therefore, various opportunities are provided for the learner in the process of learning. Educational assessment aligns with this important principle, especially in the philosophy subject, it does not merely make the learner the center of the learning process; it goes beyond, positioning the learner as the starting point for every educational and pedagogical action. The learner is granted the freedom to learn, acquire ideas, skills, knowledge, and express thoughts and perspectives, away from pressures and coercion. The learner has the freedom to pose philosophical

questions, provide answers, adopt convincing ideas and beliefs, criticize, reject, demand evidence, and make suggestions, therefore, educational assessment in the philosophy subject establishes a culture based on the learner's freedom, allowing them to practice it in the classroom with their teacher and peers – a freedom based on rational discourse and constructive positive thinking, elevating the learner to the center of the learning process as its creator and controller.

6.2 Invitation to Creativity

The educational assessment in philosophy, from the perspective of the competency-based approach, is explicitly an invitation to creativity, philosophy, being the foundation of creativity, serves as a theory for understanding, generating new ideas and products. Educational activities in philosophy, whether theoretical or practical, provide learners with ample opportunities to express their opinions, present new ideas, and articulate their internal thoughts in a logical and structured manner. For example, in writing a philosophical essay during exams, students are allowed to introduce new ideas, propose modern concepts not covered in class, and provide realistic examples that reflect and express reality. Thus, the evaluation of creativity in philosophy is positive due to its association with the concept of the standard, i.e., any standard that determine the student's position and status within the group. (Al-Masoudi, Hadi Al-Jabouri, & Hajoul Al-Jabouri, 2015, pp. 180-181)

6.3 Focus on Quality

The educational assessment in the philosophy subject, following the competency-based approach, revolves around an important idea: it establishes a pedagogy that prioritizes quality over quantity; this means an emphasis on the quality and type of knowledge in terms of accuracy, organization, and adherence to the principles of reason, logic, and intellectual foundation through argumentation and evidence.

In philosophy, what matters is not the overwhelming quantity of knowledge acquired through memorization, but rather the learner's engagement in philosophical thinking, which is referred to as "philosophical generation" by Socrates. This involves posing questions, engaging in dialectics, and other forms of discourse, philosophy values the learner's practice of philosophical activities, such as generating ideas through independent thinking. (Taha, 1987, pp. 63-64)

This concept is reflected in the evaluation of a philosophical article, where the emphasis is on the learner's ability to produce original ideas and explanations, demonstrating their contribution to philosophical thought, the assessment in philosophy touches on the learner's capabilities and creative competencies. Undoubtedly, the competency-based approach will help the evaluation process. It is a flexible approach based on observation. This means that it enables the learner to present some aspects not subject to output through tools such as text or examination. Therefore, it is difficult to convert observation into a mark or grade. (Nait Slimane, 2015, p. 82)

6.4 Reality Investment

It is acknowledged that the assessment in philosophy, according to the competency-based approach, is an assessment that reflects reality, this is because all the problems and issues discussed in philosophy are drawn from the reality of daily human life, such as political, educational, artistic, and ethical issues. These issues are expressed through a philosophical methodology that establishes thinking and attempts to understand them to provide solutions. Learners are assisted in acquiring effective methods for discussing various issues in their society, justifying assumptions is done by returning to real-life models, the competency-based approach moves the act of philosophizing from a state of abstraction in the pure mind to a state of perception and reality, it allows learners to open up to their reality, adapt to the problems of the present, and invest their acquired knowledge and skills in solving real-world problems, in this way, philosophy establishes another pedagogical path that should prevail in the learning process, focusing on thinking about the individual, society, and humanity to formulate a societal project based on relationships characterized by coexistence, harmony, and understanding, as advocated by philosophers like Kant and Russell, among others.

6.5 A Clear Message towards Intellectual and Logical Construction

Philosophy, through educational assessment following the competency-based pedagogy approach, aims to focus on the thinking individual, the learner, and make them the desired starting point for every pedagogical action, thus, concepts have shifted. Instead of focusing on teaching, the effort is directed towards learning, learning methods, tools, and mechanisms for sound thinking based on logic, which makes the active mind the starting point a mind that interacts with itself and with reality, it is not a passive mind that exists to be influenced without influencing in return, therefore, philosophy, through its various educational activities, has a clear message.

The construction of an individual's mind and their methodology of thinking. This is where the differences between philosophy and literature arise; they are contradictory, the relationship between philosophy and rhetoric is surprising. Rhetoric is considered a tool for literature, just as philosophy has its tool: logic, making tools essential to the subject matter complicates the problem. Hence, the concern for a philosophy student is to start learning logic and reasoning, as recognized by traditional Greek philosophical teachings. As for a literature student, they should refine their language skills. (Timahri & Roudh, 1993, p. 54)

From this perspective, it becomes evident that educational assessment in philosophy, within the competency-based approach, is an explicit call for intellectual and logical construction, guiding the mind towards truth and certainty.

7. Reading into the Difficulties and Obstacles Hindering the Assessment Process in Philosophy

Despite the scarcity of studies addressing philosophy as a pedagogical subject, some educators interested in education have delved into philosophy as an educational subject, by highlighting its characteristics, scholars such as Vygotsky, Pandora, Michel Tozzi, and others have explored various pedagogical processes, including assessment and its relationship with philosophy, emphasizing the distinctive features of the philosophical subject, from these features, real difficulties arise that hinder the success of the assessment process, rendering it relative, some of these difficulties include:

a- What do we Teach in Philosophy? It is widely accepted in philosophy that we do not teach philosophy as a set of lessons consisting of problems and issues presented only to students, instead, we teach them how to philosophize, meaning we do not provide them with ready-made knowledge or truths. Rather, we guide them on the path to search for and acquire knowledge after thinking, analyzing, criticizing, and examining, therefore, the value of the philosophical method, which is more important than knowledge itself, becomes evident, the renowned Moroccan thinker, Al-Taher Waezize, stated, "Teaching philosophy without the method of philosophizing is merely teaching ideas". (Waezize, 1990, p. 13)

Kant wrote in the same vein that students should not learn ideas, instead, they should learn how to think, that is, how to philosophize, consequently, philosophy is not about ready-made knowledge that we impart and teach, instead, students learn how to think, this creates a challenge in assessment, as determining the criteria for ensuring that the learner is engaging in thinking and philosophizing is complex, questions such as these pose a significant challenge to the success of the assessment process.

b- Philosophy is indeed a subject that engages in thought, analysis, synthesis, criticism, and contemplation. It presents various problems that require careful consideration, analysis, and the provision of solutions based on philosophical theories and intellectual opinions of philosophers and thinkers throughout history with their diverse tendencies, in philosophy, students immerse themselves in the language and ideas of philosophers, attempting to analyze, critique, and scrutinize, the goal of philosophical education is not for students to simply mimic philosophers whose aim was the pursuit of truth and the investigation of the principles and causes of things. Instead, students are encouraged to search for the primary causes of phenomena, drawing inspiration from the thoughts of philosophers (Fakhri, 1985, p. 16). Philosophy stands out as a subject that emphasizes critical thinking, providing a foundation for forming positions and ideologies.

However, the challenge arises in determining whether philosophical theories should be adopted as the basis for philosophical thinking or if they need to be evaluated and critiqued, additionally, the question of whether it is appropriate to critique what is not studied raises the issue of creative thinking, as long as the philosophical opinions and ideas of the past are present, this can lead to a shift in philosophy from a creative endeavor to a mere reading of what others have previously explored, consequently, the assessment of philosophy faces challenges, especially concerning the fundamental objectives we seek from studying philosophy in the first place.

c- The results in philosophy are inherently relative because they represent solutions to intellectual and philosophical problems that elicit diverse opinions and perspectives. In philosophy, the emphasis is not solely on providing answers to various issues and problems; rather, the paramount importance lies in generating questions to delve deeper into the subject. Every answer, according to philosophers like Karl Jaspers, should lead to more questions. Many philosophers assert that questions in philosophy are more crucial than answers, and each answer should transform into a new question, this distinctive feature of philosophical knowledge revolves around questioning, encompassing accurate judgment and insight immune to error. (Makawi, 1987, p. 22)

However, does philosophy always remain bound to continuous questioning? Is it futile to persist in questioning without leaning towards at least relatively certain answers? This dynamic nature of philosophical inquiry complicates the process of educational assessment in philosophy, the challenge lies in evaluating philosophical understanding when definitive answers and outcomes may not always be apparent.

d- The philosophy course is unique in that it stems from intellectual and philosophical issues that reflect reality with the aim of providing insights and solutions to various questions, here, students find themselves confronting diverse philosophical positions that study and analyze topics with conflicting opinions, philosophy always emerges from an intellectual struggle with philosophical positions on socially, politically, and educationally relevant subjects, focusing on the foundational principles and references, therefore, educational assessment in the philosophy course may find its way here, but there are obstacles and barriers that cause it to stumble due to the intertwining of issues and problems with each other.

Therefore, it can be said that the uniqueness of the philosophy course and the challenges it poses present an educational challenge, specifically in terms of educational assessment, this makes us consider the possibility of adapting educational assessment to its characteristics so that philosophy fulfills its assigned role and achieves its objectives as a subject for thought and humanity.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the educational assessment in philosophy, following the pedagogy of competency-based approaches, has added additional features to philosophy beyond its primary characteristics, it has transformed it into a subject for individual formation by equipping individuals with the mechanisms of correct thinking, urging them to engage in thought and creativity, and encouraging the practice of criticism and analysis, moreover, it has surpassed the individuality of humans to contribute to the rehabilitation of society by creating links between philosophy and the social reality of the individual, including their culture, values, and beliefs, the educational assessment, according to the competency-based approach, has introduced a new concept for philosophy, making it a bearer of a societal and humanitarian message, despite the challenges and obstacles that must be overcome, there is a need to reevaluate philosophy and its pedagogical aspects to elevate and develop it in service of both the individual and society.

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